

Article Title:

Temporal dynamics of the impact of land use on modal disparity in commuting efficiency

Journal Title:

Computer, Environment and Urban Systems

Volume and article number: **83 (101523)**

For full published version click on the DOI link:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2020.101523>

Authors:

1) NIEDZIELSKI, Michał A. (co-corresponding author)

ORCID: 0000-0001-6639-1057

Affiliation: Institute of Geography and Spatial Organization, Polish Academy of Sciences

Email: m.niedzielski@twarda.pan.pl

2) HU, Yujie (co-corresponding author)

Affiliation: a) Department of Geography, University of Florida; b) UF Informatics Institute, University of Florida

Email: yujiehu@ufl.edu

3) STĘPNIAK, Marcin

ORCID: 0000-0002-6489-5443

Scopus author ID: 21740407400

Affiliation: a) Institute of Geography and Spatial Organization, Polish Academy of Sciences, b) tGIS, Department of Geography, Complutense University of Madrid

Email: marcinstepniak@ucm.es

Abstract

Urban land use is known to affect commuting efficiency according to the excess commuting framework. However, most studies do not include temporal dynamics, and those that do, focus on decadal, yearly, or daily temporal resolutions. However, commuting is not a stationary spatial process. Since people leave home and start their jobs at different times of the day and since traffic congestion varies throughout the day, neglecting hourly dynamics can misestimate commuting efficiency in a region and lead to erroneous policy implications. Another important issue often overlooked in the past is the modal disparity in commuting efficiency and how it evolves during the day. To overcome these limitations, this research examines the commuting efficiency variation by car and public transport by six one-hour periods between 5AM and 11AM in Warsaw, Poland, using travel survey data and travel times generated from GPS-based big data for cars and from GTFS for public transport. We develop four different groups of modeling scenarios: no disaggregation, disaggregation by time, disaggregation by mode, and disaggregation by time and mode. Therefore, excess commuting and modal disparity metrics are applied for a total of 21 specific time and mode combinations. The results suggest that commuting efficiency is worst during the 8-9 AM period for both modes, and that public transport users are more efficient after 7AM. Hourly variations in the excess commuting metrics imply that policy makers should examine ways to encourage flexible work hours to distribute work starts and to increase public transport frequencies in the off-peak.

Keywords: excess commuting, temporal dynamics, modal disparity, big data, Warsaw

Acknowledgements

M. Niedzielski acknowledges the support of the Polish National Science Centre, within the POLONEZ programme, allocated on the basis of the decision no. UMO-2015/19/P/HS4/04067, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 665778. The views and opinions expressed herein reflect those of the authors only and neither the Research Executive Agency nor the Polish National Science Centre are liable for the potential use of the information contained herein.

Y. Hu would like to acknowledge the support by a grant from the Center for Transportation Equity, Decisions and Dollars (CTEDD) funded by U.S. Department of Transportation Research and Innovative Technology Administration (OST-R).

M. Stępniaak would like to thank the Spanish Agencia Estatal de Investigación (Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades) and the European Social Fund for their financial support through the Ramón y Cajal Programme.

1. Introduction

Excess commuting, also known as wasteful commuting when first introduced by Hamilton (1982), is a metric that reflects to what extent the actual commuting length in a city, such as distance or time, deviates from the theoretical minimum value. Mathematically, it is defined as the proportion of the observed commute that is over the minimum commute suggested by the existing spatial distribution of housing and jobs (Horner, 2002; Hu and Wang, 2019; White, 1988). In essence, this metric captures a city's overall commuting efficiency by quantifying the potential for a city to reduce the overall commuting length to an expected lower bound without changing the existing urban form. Therefore, it is often used as a planning tool to evaluate the performance of urban form, such as the jobs-housing balance. As the minimum commuting length describes the average shortest distance or time, that is, spatial separation, between jobs and households in a given city, it can be interpreted as a proximity-based measure of jobs-housing balance (Horner, 2008; Niedzielski, 2006). A lower minimum commute indicates a greater intermixing of employment and housing and thus a more balanced configuration of jobs and housing.

Since the invention of the excess commuting metric, many studies have raised concerns that the way to measure it—either by the classic monocentric urban model (Hamilton, 1982) or the widely-accepted linear programming approach (White, 1988)—could lead to biased and misleading estimates and policy implications. Many attempts have been made to fine-tune this metric both methodologically and conceptually. For example, one line of research is focused on taking into account heterogeneity of households and jobs, instead of treating every household or job equal, when solving the minimum commute. These efforts include, among others, the

consideration of the number of workers in a household, occupation type, neighborhood attributes, and worker mobility levels (Buliung and Kanaroglou, 2002; Cropper and Gordon, 1991; Kim, 1995; Thurston and Yezer, 1991). As the calculation of excess commuting relies on using census data at a level of aggregation, some researchers examined the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP), showing how estimates of excess commuting vary by level of aggregation (Horner and Murray, 2002; Niedzielski et al., 2013), and proposed simulation approaches to mitigate such scale effect (Hu and Wang, 2015). Conceptually, the minimum commute defines only the lower bound of a city's commute. One could not grasp the whole picture of the commute behavior in a city by examining the minimum commute alone. In this regard, some other metrics about commuting length that characterize the upper bound of a city's commute, including the theoretical maximum commute (Horner, 2002) and random commute (Charron, 2007), have been developed.

Despite these substantial efforts, many existing studies have omitted the temporal dynamics, particularly short-term, of excess commuting by calculating this metric for a region over a period of one year or longer. Nonetheless, the commuting metrics, including minimum, maximum, random, and actual commute, are subject to change in reality. For instance, the number of workers leaving home or arriving at work could vary significantly during the day. In addition, the traffic on the road network is not stationary over time but rather has peak and off-peak hours (Hu and Downs, 2019). Thus, omitting such temporal (short-term) dynamics in excess commuting could give rise to inaccurate or misleading estimates and policy implications for reducing work travel. There exist a few attempts examining the temporal instability of excess commuting, such as Frost et al. (1998) for 9 cities in UK from 1981 to 1991, Horner (2007) in

Tallahassee, Florida between 1990 and 2000, Yang (2008) in Boston and Atlanta from 1980 to 2000, and Hu and Wang (2016) between 1990 and 2010 in Baton Rouge, Louisiana. A recent effort by Zhou and Murphy (2019) assessed the *daily* variation in excess commuting in Brisbane, Australia. Clearly, except for Zhou and Murphy (2019), these studies were focused on the long-term trend of excess commuting variations. Consequently, attempts to analyze short-term instability in excess commuting are imminently needed.

Another aspect of excess commuting that has often been overlooked by existing studies is the modal disparity between private vehicle and public transport and how such disparity evolves throughout the day. Such analyses can capture to what degree land use in a city favors its car travelers and consequently reflect the sustainability of land use. Existing modal disparity studies, in the general commuting literature, have focused on examining accessibility to jobs and supermarkets (Kawabata, 2009; Niedzielski and Kucharski, 2019), while neglecting commuting efficiency. One exception by Murphy (2009) used a simple 1-on-1 comparison of excess commuting metrics between the two modes and examined how the disparity changed from 1991 to 2001. Such direct comparisons only reveal the exact value of the difference between two numbers but fail to put the difference in a standardized scale in which the comparison would be more meaningful. A more systematic measure is, therefore, warranted. Besides, knowledge about the short-term dynamics of such disparity in commuting efficiency is needed.

Using the 2015 Warsaw Traffic Survey (WTS) (Kostelecka, 2015) data collected in Warsaw, Poland, this research aims to measure the hourly temporal dynamics of excess commuting. It is

unique from existing studies in several aspects. First, to the best of our knowledge, no studies have ever looked at such a fine temporal resolution before. Second, it addresses the aforementioned issues of modal disparity in excess commuting by adapting the modal accessibility gap indicator developed in Kwok and Yeh (2004) to systematically reveal the commuting efficiency modal disparity and its short-term (hourly) dynamic patterns. Moreover, this research contributes to the literature by analyzing a much less studied European city and new big data sources.

2. Background

2.1. Commuting metrics

The *theoretical minimum commute* (T_{min}) is the lower bound of commuting in a city. In essence, it represents the commute when all workers, on average, relocate to existing housing that is closest to their jobs. This is achieved by a linear programming problem that rearranges the journey-to-work flow pattern between zones until the lowest system cost (e.g., distance or time) is found (White, 1988). Mathematically, it can be defined as:

$$\text{Minimize } T_{min} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} d_{ij} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = W_i, \sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} = J_j, x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

where x_{ij} is the optimal number of commuters living in zone i while working in zone j and it is nonnegative, d_{ij} is the travel distance (or time) between zones i and j , W_i is the total number of workers residing in zone i , J_j is the total number of jobs in zone j , m is the total number of residential zones, n is the total number of employment zones, and N is the total number of

workers in the region. The objective function minimizes the average commute and the model constraints ensure that all workers leave home and arrive at work.

The *theoretical maximum commute* (T_{max}) is proposed by Horner (2002). As opposed to T_{min} , it represents the upper bound of a city's commute where all workers, on average, relocate to housing that is the farthest from their workplace. Therefore, T_{min} and T_{max} represent a city's most efficient and least efficient commute, respectively, and together they define a city's possible commuting range or capacity. Because T_{max} is exactly the opposite scenario of T_{min} , it is equivalent to the minimization problem of negative T_{min} :

$$\text{Maximize } T_{max} = \text{Minimize } (-T_{min}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (-x_{ij} d_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = W_i, \sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} = J_j, x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

where the notations and constraints are the same as previously defined.

Some studies (Charron, 2007; Murphy and Killen, 2011) criticized T_{max} for being an unreasonable upper limit of a city's commute as the scenario where all individual workers relocate their residences in a way to maximize their commute is not likely to happen. In response, they proposed the *theoretical random commute* (T_{rnd}) as a more appropriate upper limit of a city's commute. T_{rnd} represents a travel pattern in which individual workers are insensitive to commuting costs when selecting a residence and workplace. In other words, any existing home has an equal chance of being matched to any existing job during the spatial reassignment of workers between homes and jobs. Therefore, T_{rnd} lies between the lower limit of a city's

commute T_{min} and the upper limit T_{max} . There exist two approaches to measure T_{rnd} . The first one is to generate a large random sample of commuting trips for a given city and calculate the average commuting costs. This approach has been implemented by a Markov Chain Monte Carlo method in Murphy and Killen (2011). An alternative approach, which is much less computationally demanding but can still produce highly consistent estimates, was proposed by Charron (2007) and has the following formulation:

$$T_{rnd} = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n W_{ij} J_j d_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where the notations are the same as previously stated.

2.2. Excess commuting metrics

The *excess commuting* (T_{ex}) metric (Hamilton, 1982) measures the difference between T_{min} and the observed commute (T_{obs}). It can be formulated as:

$$T_{ex} = \frac{T_{obs} - T_{min}}{T_{obs}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

T_{ex} represents the extent to which a city can optimize its commute without altering the existing jobs-housing distribution, and a greater value indicates higher commute saving potential and thus lower commuting efficiency.

By replacing T_{obs} with $T_{max} - T_{min}$ in the denominator in T_{ex} , Horner (2002) proposed another metric termed *commuting potential utilized* (T_{pu}) representing how much of the commute potential of a city has been consumed. A greater T_{pu} value means a larger proportion of a city's

commute capacity has been used and hence less efficiency in commuting. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$T_{pu} = \frac{T_{obs} - T_{min}}{T_{max} - T_{min}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Compared to T_{max} , T_{rd} is arguably a more appropriate upper limit of a city's commute.

Therefore, Murphy and Killen (2011) updated T_{pu} and developed a new metric capturing a city's commuting efficiency named *normalized commuting economy* (T_{ce}):

$$T_{ce} = \frac{T_{rd} - T_{obs}}{T_{rd} - T_{min}} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

T_{ce} calculates the extent to which T_{obs} is below T_{rd} relative to the theoretically expected range captured by $T_{rd} - T_{min}$. Larger T_{ce} values indicate larger deviations of T_{obs} from the upper commute limit T_{rd} and hence greater commuting efficiency.

Although all these excess commute metrics reflect the commuting efficiency level in a city, it is reported that no single metric can fully capture the city's commuting profile alone (Kanaroglou et al. 2015). T_{ex} , T_{pu} , and T_{ce} are complimentary because they explain different aspects of commuting behavior. For example, in a hypothetical city, $T_{min} = 5$, $T_{obs} = 8$, $T_{rd} = 12$, and $T_{max} = 15$. Then $T_{ex} = 37.5\%$, $T_{pu} = 30\%$ and $T_{ce} = 57.1\%$. If we consider the full commuting capacity, people are relatively more efficient than when the $T_{rd} - T_{min}$ range is used. Therefore, it is suggested that these metrics should be examined together.

3. Methodology

3.1 Study area

Warsaw, the capital of Poland, and its metropolitan area includes suburban cities such as Łomianki and Legionowo in the north, Marki, Wołomin, Sulejówek in the east, Otwock and Piaseczno in the south, and Piastów and Pruszków in the west (Fig. 1). There were 2,733,840 people living in the metropolitan area in 2015 (Zegar, 2016), of which 895,505 were workers including 702,030 workers commuting by the two modes studied in this paper, cars and public transport, which includes buses, trams, and subway (Kostelecka, 2015). These two modes combine for 78.4% of commute trips in the metropolitan area. Of all the car and public transport workers, 71.07% commute within the city boundary, 2.96% commute from the city to the suburbs, 11.4% commute from the suburbs to the city and 14.57% commute within the suburbs.

Warsaw's labor market reflects its role as a capital city and an alpha city in the Global and World Cities (GaWC) 2018 list (The World According to GaWC 2018, 2018). Table 1 shows that the single largest share of jobs in the city, 15.9%, is in administration, though producer services (finance, insurance, real estate, professional, information) combined account for 29.9% of all jobs in the city. Spatially jobs tend to follow major roads and railroads as shown in Figure 1. Three major job centers that emerged after 1990, are highlighted to show the impact of the restoration of property rights during the post-1990 economic transformation. Two of these, Wola and South Służewiec, are major centers of finance, insurance and information sector jobs, which emerged in former factory areas because of their regulated property rights (Górczyńska et al., 2019).

3.2 Data sources

Three major sources of data are used in this research. First, the WTS (Kostelecka, 2015), obtained from the Warsaw municipal government, provides hourly journey-to-work flows and the origin and destination totals for 895 zones in the metropolitan area. The zones average 1.98 km² in size for the whole study area, 0.62 km² within the city and 13.4 km² in the suburbs (see Figure 1). Second, car travel times are sourced from TomTom Speed Profiles data which provided traffic patterns in five-minute intervals. Third, public transport travel times are computed using the General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS). The road transport network contained in the WTS was used as the source of the pedestrian network for public transport travel times calculations.

Looking at the hourly frequency distribution of commuting trips in Figure 2, it is obvious that the majority of trips, regardless of where they start (either in the city or the suburb), peaks at 5-11AM. To be specific, the total percentages of commuting trips starting in the city and suburbs during this 6-hour range are respectively 91% and 93%. Therefore, this research examines the temporal dynamics of excess commuting and the modal disparity only within this time range, instead of the entire 24 hours. Certainly, the proposed framework, including the data sources and analytical methods, can be readily applied to other time periods of choosing.

3.3 Study design

The study design consists of four major steps. The first step involves extracting the hourly journey-to-work flow matrices and subsequently the origin and destination totals. The second

step is to calculate congested travel times for car and public transport travel for each one-hour period. Third, the various commuting metrics and excess commuting indicators described in section 2 are calculated for each of the two modes—cars and public transport—and for each hourly group. Finally, the modal commuting efficiency disparity is quantified by measuring the modal disparity gap indicator (MDG) that is detailed in section 3.5.

3.4 Travel time calculation

The calculation of travel time is a critical step in the measurement of hourly variations in commuting and excess commuting metrics. Travel time by public transport includes all trip segments, i.e. in-vehicle time, waiting time at stops, and walking: from origin to the stop, from the stop to destination, and between stops, in the case of a transfer. In order to minimize the impact of temporal resolution on travel time measurement (Stępnia et al., 2019), travel time is computed for an interval of every 5 minutes using a hybrid sampling method (Owen and Murphy, 2019) and is aggregated for each of the six one-hour periods afterwards. To compute car travel time, the TomTom[®] road network data is employed. It contains data on Speed Profiles obtained from the average journey times reported from users' navigation devices (Moya-Gómez and García-Palomares, 2017). The car travel time is computed in an interval of every 15 minutes and then averaged for each of the one-hour periods.

To obtain comparable results between both transport modes, the advanced door-to-door model (Salonen and Toivonen, 2013) is applied to adjust car travel time. Apart from in-vehicle time, for each OD pair a 10-minute penalty is added to account for the time searching for parking and

walking between a car and origin/destination point. All operations related to travel time measurement (i.e. creation of road and public transport networks and generation of origin-destination matrices) are done in ESRI[®] ArcGIS and its Network Analyst extension.

The intrazonal time, d_{ii} , is set equal to 60% of the travel time from a zone to its closest neighbor (Horner, 2010). The observed average commute distance is computed the following way:

$$T_{obs} = \frac{f_{ij}d_{ij}}{N} \quad (9)$$

where f_{ij} is the observed number of commuters living in zone i and working in zone j , with other notation as previously defined.

3.5 Modal disparity

As stated, straightforward 1-on-1 comparisons being made on a variety of excess commuting metrics between users of car and public transport could be problematic, because of a lack of a consistent scale that could lead to misinterpretation of the results. As a result, this research defines a *modal disparity gap* (MDG) index for systematically measuring the modal disparity in excess commuting. The MDG is adapted from the modal accessibility gap index that was developed by Kwok and Yeh (2004) to quantify the difference between the accessibility of private and public transport. The MDG is expressed as a ratio and is defined as:

$$MDG = \frac{T^P - T^C}{T^P + T^C} \quad (10)$$

where T^P represents the public transport excess commuting metrics and T^C describes the car metrics. The MDG is a standardized ratio ranging between -1 and 1. It has a value of -1 when T^P

reaches 0 and T^C equals any nonzero value. Take T_{ex} as an example, this scenario happens when T_{obs} reaches the optimal commute T_{min} for public transport while T_{obs} is inconsistent with T_{min} for car users in a city. On the contrary, the MDG becomes 1 when T^C is 0 and T^P has any nonzero value. Looking at T_{ex} again, this means when T_{obs} is identical to T_{min} for car users while T_{obs} is different from T_{min} for public transport users in a city. The MDG equals 0 when the same level of excess commuting, regardless of how it is measured, is observed between car and public transport users. In terms of T_{ex} , a positive MDG value indicates greater excess commute of public transport users than car users, whereas a negative MDG value denotes otherwise. Similar trends also apply to T_{pu} , where positive MDG values demonstrate more commuting potential being used for public transport (thus greater excess commute) and negative MDG values mean the opposite. Interpretations for T_{ce} are exactly the opposite, however. Positive MDG values in terms of T_{ce} indicate greater commuting efficiency for public transport (thus less excess commute) while negative values mean more excess commute. Regardless, the closer the absolute value of MDG is towards 1, the greater the excess commute disparity is between car and public transport. See Figure 3 for more details.

4. Results and discussion

In order to more fully understand the short-term temporal dynamics and modal disparity of excess commuting, four different modeling scenarios are defined as follows. The first scenario, *No disaggregation*, calculates metrics for the overall workers. This is what has been done by most existing studies in this scope. Here, it is provided as a baseline scenario. To support the analysis, travel times across both modes and six-hour periods are aggregated. The second scenario, *Disaggregate by time*, utilizes the hourly commuting and travel time matrices for the 6-

hour range and computes, for each hour period, all metric values. Comparing it with the baseline scenario can highlight the short-term temporal dynamics of excess commuting of the general workers. The third scenario, *Disaggregate by mode*, uses commuting and travel time matrices disaggregated by mode—car or public transport—measuring metrics for each mode respectively. The modal disparity in excess commuting between car and public transport users can be revealed by comparing this scenario with the baseline. In the fourth scenario, *Disaggregate by time and mode*, workers are divided into 12 subgroups—two modes by six hourly groups—and metrics are computed for each subgroup. By going a step further than scenarios 2 and 3, this scenario examines the temporal fluctuations in the modal disparity in excess commuting in Warsaw. This experiment design is notably unique from the existing literature.

Looking at results in scenario 1, it is found that Warsaw's current jobs-housing distribution could lead to an average commuting time of 16.79 minutes, (i.e., T_{min}) if no one made trips longer than required. The reality is far from the optimal case, however. In fact, an average worker is found to spend 34.56 minutes (i.e., T_{obs}) commuting, a value remarkably greater than the required one. That said, about 51.42% (i.e., T_{ex}) of the observed commute in Warsaw is more than necessary. Conversely, the upper limit of Warsaw's commute, T_{max} , is 53.18 minutes, indicating that its jobs-housing distribution supports a 36.39-minute commuting capacity ($T_{max}-T_{min}$), and nearly half of it (T_{pu} , 48.84%) has been utilized. Although measured from quite different angles, interestingly, both T_{ex} and T_{pu} imply a similar degree of commuting inefficiency (50%) in Warsaw. When Warsaw's T_{obs} is compared to an upper commute limit where cost is unimportant in locational choices, i.e. $T_{md} = 45.81$ minutes, the T_{ce} , is 38.75%, demonstrating Warsaw's

workers care less about commuting costs, closer to a random pattern. See Table 2 and Figures 4A and 4B for more details.

The foregoing results make sense in relation to the urban form of Warsaw. The jobs-housing balance of Warsaw (Figure 1) suggests a stark juxtaposition of housing-rich and jobs-rich areas with little intermixing. Most areas of the city are either housing estates (with service jobs) or office complexes (with some communist era housing especially in the central area). This means that if jobs and housing were more intermixed, then the minimum commute could be shorter. The minimum commute is also higher due to the peripheral suburban areas that contain mostly housing from which workers have to commute inward. However, the lack of job decentralization means that the maximum commute, at 53.18 minutes, is relatively short when compared to US cities, such as Los Angeles with a 92-minute T_{max} (Zhou et al., 2018). The spatial structure of the city also means that workers can find jobs without using most of the available commuting range, because either they live adjacent to jobs or they can find jobs in the central area without having to cross commute. Therefore, commuting efficiency is not as bad as it could be, again compared to Los Angeles, where $T_{ex} = 75\%$ and $T_{ce} = 7\%$.

Scenario 2 captures the hourly fluctuation patterns of excess commuting from 5 to 11 AM in Warsaw. As shown in Table 2 and Figure 4D, T_{min} is 18.12 minutes at 5-6AM, decreases by almost 3 minutes until 8-9AM when it has the lowest value of 15.32 minutes, rises by about 1.5 minutes reaching 16.87 minutes at 9-10AM and finally dropping by 0.5 minutes to 16.25 minutes at 10-11AM. The hourly T_{min} fluctuations between 5 and 11 AM highlight the short-term

temporal dynamics in commuting patterns in Warsaw and suggest the inappropriateness of treating commuting as a stationary spatial process. Instead, it swings over time due to the temporal variations in spatial distributions of employment and demand (Hu and Downs, 2019).

These temporal variations are shown in Figure 5 (only the car pattern is shown; the pattern for public transport is similar). Temporal variations in commute origins drive the metric value variations. The hourly changing patterns imply that jobs are, on average, the furthest from homes at 5-6AM during the 6-hour time window. Put another way, the intermixing of available employment and housing is the worst at 5-6AM. The first row of Figure 5 shows that this is because most workers leaving home during this period live in the suburbs and they travel to jobs in the suburbs and in the central city leading to the highest T_{min} value. While Table 2 shows that the number of available jobs increases substantially—an increase of 198% is observed from 5-6AM to 6-7AM and a 79% increase is noted from 6-7AM to 7-8AM, T_{min} declines. The second to last column of Figure 5 shows that the relative number of workers leaving home and arriving at work located at more than 15km from the central point of the city is decreasing over time (from 5 to 8AM). The last column shows that as more workers wake up and start their jobs within Warsaw and its central area, the jobs-housing balance is improving after 5-6 AM. The greatest proximity between jobs and housing appears at 8-9 AM, because this period is dominated by commuting between homes and jobs located within the city boundary (Figure 5, third column). After this period, the number of jobs drops considerably by about 60% towards 9-10AM (Table 2; Figure 5, fourth column). Understandably, these jobs tend to shrink over space and concentrate at certain job centers. This gives rise to increasing average job-home distance from 8-9AM to 9-10AM (Table 2; Figure 5, fourth column). From 9-10AM to 10-11AM, the

number of jobs further drops by 52% and the average job-home distance declines slightly (Table 2). T_{obs} increases after 9AM because jobs and housing are becoming imbalanced. A similar fluctuation pattern is also perceived for T_{rnd} and T_{max} —the values peak at 5-6AM and drop afterwards until 8-9AM, then rise again (9-10AM) and finally decline (10-11AM). An imbalanced jobs-housing distribution overall is likely to produce a larger upper bound of commuting when individual workers seek to travel to either the furthest possible employment (T_{max}) or are insensitive to distance/time (T_{rnd}). These most extreme commute values would conceivably lessen when, spatially, jobs and housing become closer. Clearly this is happening in Warsaw, as suburban workers put upward pressure on work trips lengths, while city workers put downward pressure on work trip lengths. This explains why an identical fluctuation pattern is spotted for both T_{max} and T_{rnd} with T_{min} . Note that this contradicts Murphy's (2009) finding that a reduction in T_{min} from 1991 to 2001 in Dublin, Ireland is associated with an increase in T_{max} . The inconsistency is probably because of the significant difference between long-term and short-term commute patterns and once again suggests the need for investigation into short-term dynamics in commuting.

Unlike these theoretical commute limits, the actual commute T_{obs} has an exactly contrasting fluctuation curve between 5 and 11AM. Specifically, it is the lowest (29.28 minutes) at 5-6-AM, peaks at 8-9AM (39.54 minutes), then declines towards 9-10AM and slightly bounces back at 10-11AM. This pattern makes sense, because at 8-9AM, when jobs and housing have the best spatial proximity, work- and nonwork-related traffic is the worst during the 6-hour period. All these activities during this traffic peak hour make roads the most congested and result in the greatest T_{obs} at the time when jobs and housing are overall the closest to one another. On the

contrary, the traffic at 5-6AM is the best within the 6-hour range and hence leads to the lowest T_{obs} , even though the average distance between jobs and housing is the greatest in this period. Note that the above finding is opposite to some previous studies focusing on U.S. cities. For instance, some have suggested improving the proximity between jobs and housing—i.e., promoting jobs-housing balance—could arguably lead to a reduction in actual commute (Horner, 2002; Hu and Wang, 2016). However, this policy relation does not seem to apply to Warsaw. Another factor that may contribute to the contrasting finding is that these studies examined the long-term changing patterns of commuting whereas the present study looks at the short-term dynamics instead. The findings, perhaps, suggest that it would be beneficial to take nonwork travel into account in the measurement of excess commuting, such as supermarkets stops after work (Niedzielski and Kucharski, 2019).

In terms of the 6-hour excess commuting dynamics, the three relevant metrics— T_{ex} , T_{pu} , and T_{ce} —are in agreement. Table 2 and Figure 4G show that the T_{ex} and T_{pu} values increase from 5-6AM, peak at 8-9AM, drop towards 9-10AM, and slightly rise at 10-11AM. This indicates that excess commuting in Warsaw, when measured by the $T_{obs}-T_{min}$ deviation or by how much commuting capacity has been consumed, starts the lowest at 5-6AM and gradually increases and becomes the greatest at the traffic peak hour 8-9AM. The percent increases are highly noticeable—60% for T_{ex} and 137% for T_{pu} . After then, Warsaw's commute becomes moderately more efficient at 9-10AM and then slightly inefficient again at 10-11AM. In the same vein, the commuting economy captured by T_{ce} has the highest value at 5-6AM, indicating the greatest commute efficiency in this period, then dropping toward the worst efficiency at 8-9AM. The commute becomes more economized at 9-10AM but less efficient at 10-11AM.

Scenario 3 disaggregates excess commuting by modes. Comparing scenario 3 metric values with the same metric values in the baseline scenario can highlight, at least partly, the modal disparity in commuting patterns and efficiency. For example, values of the commuting metrics (T_{min} , T_{obs} , T_{rd} , and T_{max}) for public transport are significantly higher (16.37%, 35.13%, 39.75%, and 40.94%, respectively) than the values for the general case where mode is not explicitly considered. It also means that these values for cars are equivalently lower than those for the general case. Such differences between public transport and cars indicate significant modal disparity in Warsaw's commute. It appears that the combination of the jobs-housing distribution, and public transport network layout and schedules in Warsaw has determined that public transport commuters, on average, *need to* (as reflected by T_{min}) travel longer (16.37% more) than their car counterparts and they indeed do (indicated by T_{obs}) travel extra (by 35.13%) than car commuters. Accordingly, significantly greater excess commuting (T_{ex}) is observed for public transport users than car users; clearly public transport users are less efficient commuters in Warsaw. This is largely due to the greater flexibility in car travel than public transport. In essence, public transport routes are less developed and connected than the street network, and the timetabling restrictions in public transport service add another layer of potentially extra travel than car. Therefore, public transport commuters have greater theoretical required and actual commutes, as well as excess commute, than car commuters. When measured by T_{pu} and T_{ce} , excess commuting results are different because, relative to general commuters, public transport commuters use slightly less commuting capacity so are more efficient (car users slightly more and less efficient). This may support the statement by Kanaroglou et al. (2015) that it is better to use multiple excess commuting metrics to study a city's commuting pattern as no single metric

can fully capture it alone. But it appears that the differences in values between the two modes are more remarkable in T_{ex} than in T_{pu} or T_{ce} . Perhaps, this suggests that T_{ex} performs better in discovering modal disparity than other analogous metrics. As argued previously, it may be ineffective to discover modal disparity based on straightforward 1-on-1 comparisons between public transport's and car's excess commuting metrics. For instance, the difference of T_{min} , T_{obs} , T_{rnd} , and T_{max} between the two modes is 6.91, 24.28, 36.42, and 42.5 minutes, respectively. But which metric suggests the most prominent modal disparity? This would not be simple to tackle as these deviations do not have a consistent measurement scale. Instead, the MDG measures the disparity between two metrics, regardless of what their definitions are, always in the range of -1 and 1. According to Figure 3 and Table 2, Warsaw's public transport commuters are less efficient than car users based on T_{ex} (MDG = 0.142). However, the MDG based on T_{pu} (-0.004) suggests trivially greater inefficiency of car users. Similarly, the T_{ce} MDG (0.059) implies less efficiency in car commuters. The use of an upper bound on commuting potential in a region in T_{pu} and T_{ce} as well as the consistent scale of MDG make the interpretations comparable and less subjective. Because travel times are at different scales (public transport users generally travel longer), a commuting upper bound is needed (T_{max} or T_{rnd}) for a meaningful intermodal comparison (public transport users generally consume less commuting capacity); otherwise modal disparity based on T_{ex} is misleading (a larger T_{obs} value for public transport results in a larger T_{ex} value). Instead, T_{ex} can be an appropriate commuting efficiency metric for comparison for a single mode.

Scenario 4 further sheds light on short-term dynamics of modal commuting disparity. As shown in Table 2 and Figures 4E, 4F, 4H, and 4I, all the public transport or car metrics show similar

fluctuations as the general commuters (Figures 4D and 4G) over the 6-hour period, hence indicating an increasing degree of inefficiency in commute from 5 to 9AM for both travel modes. To better illustrate the dynamics of excess commute modal disparity, the MDG values for the three excess commuting metrics, are plotted against the time (Figure 4C). Clearly, commute efficiency modal disparity is not stationary, but rather has distinct peaks and pits. The T_{ex} curve shows that public transport users are consistently less efficient in their commutes. However, the disparity between the two modes narrows greatly (about 45% decrease) from 5AM until 9AM and then increases afterwards. The closing modal disparity gap is driven by the greater increasing rate (76%) in car commuting inefficiency (T_{ex}) than that of public transport (45%) from 5 to 9AM. As expected, T_{pu} and T_{ce} MDGs return a different shifting pattern compared to T_{ex} , but are more realist because they are based on the full commuting capacity. Note that the opposing curve pattern between T_{pu} and T_{ce} is because of the exactly opposite interpretations of their values as explained in section 3.5. Between 5 and 7AM, public transport because they are based on the full commuting capacity appear to commute less efficiently than their car counterparts, based on T_{ex} . However, after 7AM, the disparity is reversed, as car users are inefficient commuters. The results and findings from above suggest significant temporal dynamics in commuting patterns and efficiency as well as modal disparity, which would have not been possible by existing methods and datasets.

5. Conclusions

Using travel survey data and big GPS-based travel time data, this paper systematically explores the hourly variation in jobs-housing balance and commuting efficiency by mode in Warsaw,

Poland. Through the lens of the excess commuting framework, this research captures the impact of land use on commuting, disaggregated by mode and hour.

Excess commuting is an important indicator of commuting efficiency and commute reduction potential which can provide useful policy implications. The relevant question for policy that this paper tackles by using hourly commuting slices is how commuting efficiency varies every hour in the morning for cars and public transport. This paper uncovers temporal variations in land use patterns which is different from previous papers which consider daily, yearly or decadal temporal resolutions. Longer term variations are more obvious given new homes and offices are built and have their own policy implications in terms of where new and infill development should be located to reduce work travel. The focus in the longer term is on changes to the physical landscape of homes and jobs. Hourly variations and their implications are less obvious. While the physical land use pattern does not change by hour, how it is used by workers does change significantly by hour. Workers in Warsaw who live farther away from their jobs, such as those living in the suburbs, start their day earlier (before 7 AM) than others and much later than others (after 10 AM), while those working and living in the central area start their day mid-morning (between 7 and 9 AM). T_{min} shows the difference between early and mid-morning risers is 2.8 minutes for both modes combined (3.82 minutes for public transport, 1.08 minutes for cars). T_{obs} , however, shows an opposite trend, as mid-morning workers commute 10.28 minutes more than early risers (13.52 minutes for public transport, 7 minutes for cars). Congestion clearly has an impact on commuting efficiency, but one of the major findings of this paper shows that public transport outperforms cars in terms of commuting efficiency in two ways. First, in the most congested period (8-9 AM) T_{obs} , T_{pu} and T_{ce} are at the highest level for both modes, but public

transport users are much more efficient users as shown by the MDG values based on T_{pu} and T_{ce} . Second, public transport users are more efficient in their commutes after 7 AM showing that public transport schedules impact commute efficiency: higher frequency between 7 and 9 AM leads to less waiting time for public transport and shorter travel times. These hourly variations imply that policy makers should examine ways to encourage flexible work hours to distribute work starts and to increase public transport frequencies in the off-peak (before 7 AM and after 9 AM).

There are several directions for future research. First, smaller temporal resolutions, such as 15 or 30 minutes, should be considered to explore the sensitivity of modal disparity in commuting efficiency to various levels of temporal aggregation. Second, how the temporal dynamics of commuting efficiency vary spatially within the city should be explored. Third, how the hourly impact of land use on commuting varies by different population groups, such as education, job skills, and race/ethnicity should also be explored. Fourth, these findings are unique to Warsaw, Poland, so an international comparison of the temporal dynamics of modal disparity in commuting efficiency is warranted.

References

- 1) Buliung, R. N., & Kanaroglou, P. S. (2002). Commute minimization in the Greater Toronto Area: applying a modified excess commute. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 10(3), 177-186. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0966-6923\(02\)00010-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0966-6923(02)00010-8)
- 2) Cacko, A. (2018). Statistical Yearbook of Warsaw. Report by Urząd Statystyczny w Warszawie. https://warszawa.stat.gov.pl/download/gfx/warszawa/pl/defaultaktualnosci/752/6/15/1/rocznik_warszawy_2018.pdf Accessed: 18.12.2019.
- 3) Charron, M. (2007). From excess commuting to commuting possibilities: more extension to the concept of excess commuting. *Environment and Planning A*, 39(5), 1238-1254. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a3897>
- 4) Cropper, M. L., & Gordon, P. L. (1991). Wasteful commuting: a re-examination. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 29(1), 2-13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0094-1190\(91\)90022-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0094-1190(91)90022-Y)
- 5) Frost, M., Linneker, B., & Spence, N. (1998). Excess or wasteful commuting in a selection of British cities. *Transportation Research Part A*, 32(7), 529-538. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0965-8564\(98\)00016-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0965-8564(98)00016-0)
- 6) Górczyńska, M., Śleszyński, P., & Niedzielski, M.A. (2019). Impact of property rights and ownership on the development of Warsaw's contemporary city centre. *European Planning Studies*, 27(1), 160-180. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2018.1531975>
- 7) Hamilton, B. W. (1982). Wasteful commuting. *Journal of Political Economy*, 90(5), 1035-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261844>
- 8) Horner, M. W. (2002). Extensions to the concept of excess commuting. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 34(3), 543-566. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a34126>

- 9) Horner, M. W. (2008). 'Optimal' Accessibility Landscapes? Development of a New Methodology for Simulating and Assessing Jobs—Housing Relationships in Urban Regions. *Urban Studies*, 45(8), 1583-1602. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098008091492>
- 10) Horner, M. W. (2010). Exploring the sensitivity of jobs-housing statistics to imperfect travel time information. *Environment and Planning B*, 37, 367-375. <https://doi.org/10.1068/b35094>
- 11) Horner, M. W., & Murray, A. T. (2002). Excess commuting and the modifiable areal unit problem. *Urban Studies*, 39(1), 131-139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980220099113>
- 12) Hu, Y., & Downs, J. (2019). Measuring and visualizing place-based space-time job accessibility. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 74, 278-288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2018.12.002>
- 13) Hu, Y., & Wang, F. (2015). Decomposing excess commuting: A Monte Carlo simulation approach. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 44, 43-52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2015.03.002>
- 14) Hu, Y., & Wang, F. (2016). Temporal trends of intraurban commuting in Baton Rouge, 1990–2010. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 106(2), 470-479. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00045608.2015.1113117>
- 15) Hu, Y., & Wang, F. (2019). *GIS-based Simulation and Analysis of Intra-urban Commuting*. CRC Press.
- 16) Kanaroglou, P. S., Higgins, C. D., & Chowdhury, T. A. (2015). Excess commuting: a critical review and comparative analysis of concepts, indices, and policy implications. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 44, 13-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2015.02.009>
- 17) Kawabata, M. (2009). Spatiotemporal dimensions of modal accessibility disparity in Boston and San Francisco. *Environment and Planning A*, 41, 183–198. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a4068>

- 18) Kim, S. (1995). Excess commuting for two-worker households in the Los Angeles metropolitan area. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 38(2), 166-182.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/juec.1995.1027>
- 19) Kostelecka, A. (2015) Warszawskie Badanie Ruchu 2015 wraz z opracowaniem modelu ruchu. Raport z etapu III. Opracowanie wyników badań.
http://transport.um.warszawa.pl/sites/default/files/WBR%202015.%20Etap%20III.%20Raport.%20Wersja%2006_2016.pdf Accessed: 27.04.2017 [in Polish].
- 20) Kwok, R. C., & Yeh, A. G. (2004). The use of modal accessibility gap as an indicator for sustainable transport development. *Environment and Planning A*, 36(5), 921-936.
<https://doi.org/10.1068/a3673>
- 21) Moya-Gómez, B., & García-Palomares, J. C. (2017). The impacts of congestion on automobile accessibility. What happens in large European cities? *Journal of Transport Geography*, 62, 148–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2017.05.014>
- 22) Moya-Gómez, B., Salas-Olmedo, M.H., García-Palomares, J.C., Gutiérrez, J., 2018. Dynamic Accessibility using Big Data: The Role of the Changing Conditions of Network Congestion and Destination Attractiveness. *Networks and Spatial Economics* 18, 273–290.
doi:10.1007/s11067-017-9348-z
- 23) Murphy, B., & Owen, A. (2019). Temporal sampling and service frequency harmonics in transit accessibility evaluation. *Journal of Transport and Land Use*, 12(1), 893–913.
<https://doi.org/10.5198/jtlu.2019.1379>
- 24) Murphy, E. (2009). Excess commuting and modal choice. *Transportation Research Part A*, 43(8), 735-743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2009.07.004>

- 25) Murphy, E., & Killen, J. E. (2011). Commuting economy: An alternative approach for assessing regional commuting efficiency. *Urban Studies*, 48(6), 1255-1272.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098010370627>
- 26) Niedzielski, M.A., 2006, A spatially disaggregated approach to commuting efficiency, *Urban Studies*, 43(13): 2485-2502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980600970672>
- 27) Niedzielski, M. A., Horner, M. W., & Xiao, N. (2013). Analyzing scale independence in jobs-housing and commute efficiency metrics. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 58, 129-143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2013.10.018>
- 28) Niedzielski, M.A., & Kucharski, R. (2019). Impact of commuting, time budgets, and activity durations on modal disparity in accessibility to supermarkets. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 75: 106-120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2019.08.021>
- 29) Salonen, M., & Toivonen, T. (2013). Modelling travel time in urban networks: comparable measures for private car and public transport. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 31, 143–153.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2013.06.011>
- 30) Stępnia, M., Goliszek, S., 2017. Spatio-Temporal Variation of Accessibility by Public Transport—The Equity Perspective, in: Ivan, I., Singleton, A., Horák, J., Inspektor, T. (Eds.), *The Rise of Big Spatial Data*. Springer, pp. 241–261. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-45123-7_18
- 31) Stępnia, M., Pritchard, J. P., Geurs, K. T., & Goliszek, S. (2019). The impact of temporal resolution on public transport accessibility measurement: Review and case study in Poland. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 75, 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2019.01.007>
- 32) The World According to GaWC 2018. (2018).
<https://www.lboro.ac.uk/gawc/world2018t.html> Accessed: 18.12.2019

- 33) Thurston, L., & Yezer, A. M. (1991). Testing the monocentric urban model: evidence based on wasteful commuting. *Real Estate Economics*, 19(1), 41-51. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6229.00539>
- 34) White, M. J. (1988). Urban commuting journeys are not "wasteful". *Journal of Political Economy*, 96(5), 1097-1110. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261579>
- 35) Yang, J. (2008). Policy implications of excess commuting: examining the impacts of changes in US metropolitan spatial structure. *Urban Studies*, 45(2), 391-405. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098007085969>
- 36) Zegar, T (2016). Obszar Metropolitalny Warszawy w 2015 r. Report by Urząd Statystyczny w Warszawie. https://warszawa.stat.gov.pl/download/gfx/warszawa/pl/defaultaktualnosci/760/15/8/1/omw_2015.pdf Accessed: 6.12.2019 [in Polish].
- 37) Zhou, J., Murphy, E., & Corcoran, J. (2018). Integrating road carrying capacity and traffic congestion into the excess commuting framework: The case of Los Angeles. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science* <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808318773762>
- 38) Zhou, J., & Murphy, E. (2019). Day-to-day variation in excess commuting: An exploratory study of Brisbane, Australia. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 74, 223-232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2018.11.014>

National Employment Section	Percentage of total
administrative, incl. public	15,9%
trade	15,9%
finance, insurance, real estate	12,5%
professional, scientific, technical	10,0%
education	8,9%
industry	8,7%
information, communication	7,4%

transportation	6,5%
human health, social work	5,0%
construction	4,5%
accomodation and catering	2,4%
arts, entertainment, recreation	1,7%
other services	0,6%
agriculture, forestry, fishing	0,1%

Table 1. Labor market according to national employment sections in the city of Warsaw (Cacko, 2018).

Scenario		N	T_{min}	T_{obs}	T_{rnd}	T_{max}	T_{ex}	T_{pu}	T_{ce}	MDG			
										T_{ex}	T_{pu}	T_{ce}	
No disaggregation		702,030	16.79	34.56	45.81	53.18	51.42	48.84	38.75	—			
Disaggregate by time	5 – 6 AM	52,501	18.12	29.28	47.94	56.15	38.11	29.35	62.58	—			
	6 – 7 AM	156,582	17.79	30.14	47.70	55.84	40.97	32.45	58.72				
	7 – 8 AM	280,688	16.50	35.18	45.44	53.22	53.10	50.87	35.45				
	8 – 9 AM	133,087	15.32	39.54	42.63	50.09	61.25	69.66	11.34				
	9 – 10 AM	53,786	16.87	35.08	46.44	54.40	51.91	48.53	38.40				
	10 – 11 AM	25,386	16.25	37.34	45.00	52.77	56.49	57.75	26.63				
Disaggregate by mode	P		418,163	19.54	46.70	64.02	74.95	58.16	49.02	38.93	0.142	-0.004	0.059
	C		283,867	12.63	22.42	27.60	32.45	43.68	49.40	34.57			
Disaggregate by time and mode	5 – 6 AM	P	31,273	21.34	39.70	67.88	80.20	46.25	31.20	60.54	0.207	0.047	-0.008
		C	21,228	13.12	18.85	28.00	33.30	30.41	28.41	61.47			
	6 – 7 AM	P	93,276	20.72	40.49	66.86	79.20	48.83	33.81	57.15	0.187	0.024	0.002
		C	63,306	13.17	19.79	28.55	33.70	33.46	32.24	56.97			
	7 – 8 AM	P	167,195	18.96	47.18	62.92	74.74	59.80	50.59	35.81	0.138	-0.018	0.068
		C	113,493	12.67	23.18	27.95	32.72	45.32	52.41	31.24			
	8 – 9 AM	P	79,274	17.52	53.22	58.70	70.06	67.09	67.96	13.31	0.114	-0.032	0.461
		C	53,813	12.04	25.85	26.56	31.09	53.41	72.49	4.91			
	9 – 10 AM	P	32,027	19.69	47.63	65.20	77.41	58.66	48.10	38.61	0.143	-0.015	0.061
		C	21,759	12.62	22.54	27.69	32.53	44.00	49.84	34.15			
	10 – 11 AM	P	15,118	18.97	50.92	63.13	75.04	62.75	56.98	27.64	0.129	-0.021	0.129
		C	10,268	12.27	23.76	26.88	31.63	48.39	59.39	21.31			

Note: N denotes the total number of commuters, P represents public transport, C means car travel, and — indicates not available; T_{min} , T_{obs} , T_{rnd} , and T_{max} are in minutes; and T_{ex} , T_{pu} , and T_{ce} are in percentages.

Table 2. Results of excess commuting metrics.

Figure 1. Jobs Workers Ratio (JWR) in the Warsaw metropolitan area. JWR calculated as: $JWR_i = (J_j - W_i)/(J_j + W_i)$. A positive JWR value indicates a jobs-rich zone (red), while a negative JWR value indicates a housing-rich zone (green). Some major job centers are highlighted, such as the main center around Parade Square and three centers with financial and information technology jobs: Wola (labeled 1), North Mokotów (labeled 2), and South Służewiec (labeled 3).

Figure 2. Frequency distribution of commuting trips by the hour of the day in Warsaw.

Figure 3. The range and interpretation of MDG.

A) Commuting metrics aggregated over 5-11 AM

B) Excess commuting metrics aggregated over 5-11 AM

C) MDG index disaggregated by time

D) Commuting metrics of both modes, disaggregated by time

E) Commuting metrics of public transit, disaggregated by time

F) Commuting metrics of car, disaggregated by time

Figure 4. Plots of A) commuting metrics aggregated over 5-11 AM, B) excess commuting metrics aggregated over 5-11 AM, C) MDG index disaggregated by time, D) commuting metrics of both modes, disaggregated by time, E) commuting metrics of public transit, disaggregated by time, F) commuting metrics of car, disaggregated by time, G) excess commuting metrics of both modes, disaggregated by time, H) excess commuting metrics of public transit, disaggregated by time, I) excess commuting metrics of car, disaggregated by time. [Note: for better visualization, T_{ce} is plotted on the right vertical axis in C), T_{min} is plotted on the right vertical axis in D), E), and F).]

Figure 5. Standardized and absolute number of workers and jobs by hour period by car in the Warsaw metropolitan area. The standardized values for each hour are scaled by dividing them by the maximum zonal number of workers/jobs for each hour in the metropolitan area.